

Utilization of Speaking Games Through Blended Learning for Developing Speaking English of Secondary School Students and Motivation to Speak

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Abstract

This study was conducted to investigate the use of speaking games through blended learning as a pedagogical Technique in teaching English language, and its impact on students' speaking skills. This Study is conducted quantitative data through the use of pre/post speaking tests, a motivation scale, and scoring rubric as data collecting instruments. These instruments were administered to first year secondary school students. The results showed that Speaking Games through Blended Learning can provide learners with all the communicative elements that allow them to use English to express their ideas freely. This offers an indication of how useful Speaking Games through Blended Learning are when encouraging students to learn English.

Keywords: - Speaking Games, Blended Learning, EFL speaking skills, secondary School Students.

Introduction

Speaking is all special, and is used to communicate and make relationship between people in the world because it is one of the abilities to make conversation. To speak English is hard, because the speaker should also take care of some important elements, such as pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary fluency and comprehension. Speaking is an interactive process in constructing meaning that involves producing, receiving and processing information. English learners should have the ability of English speaking in order to communicate with others. (Nabil Hussien, 2016)

Speaking is one of the most important skills in English. People who can speak English will get many advantages of their ability. For instance, those who can speak English will be better in education and work than those who cannot speak English. Many students, while they study English at university, yet they cannot speak English well because some English teachers focus on teaching the grammar only. (Lufhia hanum, 2018).

In education, listening and speaking as language skills get less care within the other English skills teaching and learning. The teachers too often teach reading and writing. Some teachers assume that giving the students writing and reading tasks make them more settled and quieter and seem to urge a better and simpler condition of teaching-learning process instead of giving them speaking tasks which usually seem to make the class very noisy. In addition, searches in education give an excessive amount of proportion in reading-writing test. There are rarely speaking tests or oral production tests, consequently the teachers assume that listening and speaking aren't very important to check. (Lia Nirmawati , 2015).

The most common difficulties in speech that were observed during teaching speaking were:

1. Students frequently have no idea what to say, so they prefer to remain silent.
2. They are often shy and awkward, and they are not sure if they make mistakes.
3. Students are afraid of making mistakes in class because they would be laughed at. (Hendra Heriansyah ,2012).

Such problems require researchers to find methods that can help learners develop their speaking ability , motivate them to speak and that cope with the spirit of the age .Blended learning is a recent trend that is being utilized by educational system around the world including Egypt , and educational language games proved in many researches to be effective and motivating in learning English .A method that combines blended learning and speaking games can meet the conditions of the required methods stated above.

Blended learning is a new method of combining a face-to-face classroom component with the best use of technology. The term technology refers to a variety of recent developments, such as the internet, CD–Roms and interactive white board. It also

includes the use of computers as a means of communication, such as chat and email, and a number of environments which enable teachers to enrich their courses. (Naila Abu-sheera, 2015).

Blended learning is very useful for students in learning English because it enables them to practice language inside and outside the class room, which enhances their ability in the language skills, particularly speaking skills. (Naila Abu-sheera, 2015).

In addition to its role and educational value, games help learners achieve their goals by providing engaging and humorous content. Games, on the other hand, must be used in a specific setting. To properly implement gamified design in the classroom, you must first prepare. Student-to-student and student-to-teacher interaction can both benefit from games strategies. The learning process is motivated and tension is reduced in a communicative setting. Games promote critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. Many EFL teachers struggle with their students' lack of motivation and passiveness, which results in their inability to speak and participate in English .(Wafa Alfulaih,2017)

According to Abd Elrizig Ibrahim (2017) the advantages of games in learning are the following:

1. Games are learner-centered (the student is always in focus).
2. Games promote a communicative competence.
3. Games create a meaningful context for language use.
4. Games increase learning motivation.
5. Games reduce learning anxiety.
6. Games integrate many various linguistic skills.
7. Games encourage creativity and spontaneous usage of the language.
8. Games construct a cooperative learning environment.
9. Games foster participatory attitudes of the students.

Research and the suggested methods:

Many worldwide researches have tackled the importance of blended learning and speaking games and reached some good and promising conclusions in relation to utilizing them for language development purpose. The following previous studies are some of them:

Rahmawati (2019) investigated that blended learning supports the enhancement of students' speaking and listening skills, the study aimed to explore the students' voice on blended learning implementation in the Listening and Speaking for Formal Setting course at one Islamic Private University in Yogyakarta also investigated the students' choice on their class mode preference for other future courses: full face-to-face or the combination of both face-to-face and online modes. Six English Language Education Department (ELED) freshmen who enrolled the course were chosen using snowball sampling technique to participate in this study. Using an in-depth interview and observation of the online learning course

website, this study indicated that the blended learning model being designed was appropriate for the students’ learning needs. Besides, the students perceived that blending the face-to face with the online meetings for the listening and speaking course was an effective delivery mode for the following reasons: various learning materials, interactive yet challenging activities, appropriate to the students’ proficiency level, relevant to the course syllabus, flexible, and improved language skills. Regarding which delivery mode the participants prefer, the majority indicated to have a blended learning mode for their other future courses

Wang (2020) conducted that teaching English conversation in both online and offline settings can enhance learners’ communicative performance as well as feedback from both teachers and students. A pre-experimental method was used to investigate the effect of blended learning on the English speaking and listening performance of 136 participants, who were divided into 3 groups and invited to join an 18-week English conversation course based on both face-to-face teaching and online learning. The data was collected and analyzed from the students’ pre-test and post-test scores, a questionnaire survey and semi-structured interviews. As expected, the results indicated that blended learning had an overall great effect on the students’ English speaking performance. The students themselves had a positive attitude toward the blended course arrangement and agreed that blended learning supported their learning of English conversation, while the teachers also indicated that the online course had helped the students’ learning of English conversation to some extent. However, for a more thorough preparation of blended learning, additional encouraging policies are needed. In order to create a mixed English conversation course and show its effectiveness, Hitutor was used in this study. The limitations of an EFL learning environment can be addressed by non-native English speakers using both traditional lectures and ICT.

The design of the study:

This study used a quasi-experimental design with included quantitative research methods. This is because the research was designed to examine the impact of both games and blended learning on EFL learners' speaking abilities. A one-group pre-posttest quasi-experimental approach was used to accomplish the goal. Twenty five students, who have been studying English as a foreign language for almost ten years, took part in the program. Both quantitative techniques were utilized to analyze the data more thoroughly. The researcher employed three instruments as part of the mixed approach design. The statistical analysis of the outcomes was done using the SPSS software.

In this design, a researcher first collects and analyzes the quantitative (numeric) data.

A one group pre/posttest quasi-experimental design was used to achieve this goal. This study used a quantitative way to clarify how and why the outcomes happened as a form of explanation for the quantitative results when analyzing the data. The quantitative method was based on statistical analysis of the results of executing the strategy. The participants took a speaking exam before and after the treatment in addition to a rating scale to compare their performance.

Fig 4

One-Group Pretest-Posttest (Örnek, 2007)

A is treatment group

O1 ---- Is the pretest

X ---- Is the treatment. (The suggested strategy)

O2 ---- Is the posttest

Implementation Procedures:

1. After the program had been designed, it was ready for implementation, and investigating its effect on developing the target speaking sub skills. This required preparing instruments. Two tests were designed, verified and used for pre / post application before and after studying the program; a quantitative instrument and qualitative instruments
2. Having designed the target program and the research instruments, the treatment was to be carried out.
3. An orientation session was held to inform the participants of the aims, the requirements, the procedures, roles of participants, and the researcher (as a teacher), the benefits they can get (for motivating them to participate in the experiment), the time and duration of the program.
4. Pre-testing the participants: the speaking pretest was carried prior to conducting the experiment.
5. Preparing the physical environment in which the study was to be implemented, an appropriate class room equipped with all necessary facilities such as the smart board, tablets and the internet.
6. Starting the experiment with the first online zoom session and the follow up session then proceeding according to plan of implementation..
7. During implementation, it was essential that the teacher use a particular motivational technique. She had to be particularly careful to handle the

participants in a positive and motivational way. Additionally, she had to insist on exercising discussion ethics and skills and encourage participant involvement and cooperation. All of these factors contributed to creating the ideal psychological setting needed to maximize the likelihood of successful learning.

8. In addition to the use of a motivation strategy, the researcher was concerned with achieving the following to maximize the effectiveness of the speaking games:
 - A. Clarity of objectives of the session to participants
 - B. Telling participants of all requirements of the experiment: their roles, the activities, how to behave during the program, how to interact with peers, and how to respond to items of the instruments of evaluation. This helped participants to start the program and do what was required.
 - C. Telling participants of the expected benefits of studying the program to encourage them to study the content and afford all possible discomforts.
 - D. Achieving punctuality adhering to schedule of work and not wasting time in useless.
 - E. Clarity from the researcher (teacher).
 - F. Using appropriate question asking and error connection techniques.
 - G. Assigning interesting and rewarding homework.
 - H. Providing constructive feedback.
 - I. Promoting interaction and using rapport building techniques. the experiment and posing recommendations at the end of the study.
9. Administering the post test.
10. Results were concluded and then analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively.
11. Accordingly and in the light of the results and the analysis, a set of recommendations addressing EFL teachers, course designers and future researchers were offered.

Second: Implementation Procedures:

The strategy Implementation

This treatment was conducted in class during the first term of the academic year (2022/2023) the following steps were adhered to;

Warm-up

This stage was called ice-breaking stage which was achieved through holding an introductory session to the students. It was held directly after the researcher had told the students about the treatment and how it is different from their daily regular classroom teaching, at this introductory session, the researcher told the students about the treatment: its objectives, its rationale and how they will benefit from it.

Increasingly, the researcher gave her what's app number to the students to join a pre-created group for them and she told them to download zoom application and the right steps to make the account

Hence, the participants were enthusiastic to participate in the treatment.

Lately, online. She sent them a link to join the group and sent a zoom link to try to join the online session with her, first there were some difficulties but then they could join.

The Application Step

The researcher started with the administration of the pre-test. Then, the researcher told the group about the weekly teaching times. They used to meet them two days a week (two online and other two offline) according to the school timetable. The meeting or teaching time lasted for about forty-five minutes two times a week in classroom (15 minutes online). After that, the teacher started playing the games treatment as follows:

- Playing the games inside the classroom
- Each lesson plan followed the same sequence of the adopted program Components. The designed games treatment included some of English-speaking skills which are (accuracy, fluency and motivation to speak).

The results:

In order to determine the effect size of the Speaking Games through Blended Learning on of the accuracy in speaking performance of the experimental group, Eta Square (η^2) was calculated as illustrated in table (1)

Table (1) The Effect of Speaking Games through Blended Learning Strategy on the accuracy in speaking performance of the experimental group

Sub-skill of RC	N	Effect size
pronunciation	25	0.922
stress	25	0.957
vocab	25	0.967
grammar	25	0.974
expression	25	0.961
All Test accuracy	25	0.983

Results in table (6) indicate that the effect size (η^2) ranged from (0.922 to 0.983). The effect size percentages are (92.2%, 95.7%, 96.7%, 97,4%, 96,1% 98,3% respectively). This indicates a high effect size for all accuracy sub-skills of the experimental treatment. These results are illustrated as in figure (1).

Estimating the effect size:

In order to determine the effect size of the Speaking Games Through Blended Learning on of the fluency in speaking performance of the experimental group, Eta square (η^2) was calculated as illustrated in table (2)

Table (2) The Effect of speaking games through blended learning Strategy on the fluency in speaking performance of the experimental group

Sub-skill of RC	N	Effect size
Rate	25	0.963
without	25	0.979
duration	25	0.975
All Test fluency	25	0.976

Results in table (8) indicate that the effect size (25) ranged from (0.644 to 0.961). The effect size percentages are (73.7%, 93.9%, 86%, 64.4%, 81.7 respectively). This indicates a high effect size for all fluency sub-skills of the experimental treatment. These results are illustrated as in figure (9).

Estimating the effect size:

In order to determine the effect size of the Speaking Games Through Blended Learning strategy on of the Motivation performance of the experimental group, Eta square (η^2) was calculated as illustrated in table (3)

Table (3) The Effect Size of Mental Imagery Strategy on the Motivation performance of the experimental group

skill of RC	N	Effect size
Attitude Toward Learning to Speak English	25	0.948
Speaking Motivational Intensity	25	0.970
Motivation	25	0.971

Results in table (10) indicate that the effect size (25) ranged from (0.0.948 to 0.971). The effect size percentages are (94.8%,97.0%,97.1% respectively). This indicates a high effect size for all story reading comprehension sub-skills of the experimental treatment. These results are illustrated as in figure (9).

Discussion

The results will be discussed in terms of speaking competency overall as well as the two major speaking skills, fluency and accuracy. Overall post-test on speaking The Speaking Games treatment increased students' overall speaking competency, according to the t-test findings. This indicates that the treatment group significantly improved their general speaking skills. In order to improve the treatment group students' speaking performance, the treatment may has been successful. It is significant that all the factors that led to a notable improvement in the speaking elements (fluency and accuracy) also contributed to the experimental group students' overall FL speaking ability.

- Recommendations of the Study

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations for further research can be made:

Teachers

EFL teachers must use speaking activities that incorporate real life situations and meaningful contexts. Before deciding on these activities, EFL teachers need to identify the needs and interests of the target students. EFL teachers must provide their students with a relaxing atmosphere while learning especially if he / she tend to enhance the pupils ' oral performance. EFL teachers should focus equally on the different speaking skills taking into account to focus more on fluency of speaking since fluency leads to accuracy but not the opposite. EFL teachers must not tolerate using the native language when they find it difficult to express them using the target language since if it is tolerated once, it will be difficult to be controlled. EFL teachers must always use a rewarding system, give positive feedbacks

EFL Curriculum Designer's According to the recommendations can be considered during course design.

Following Speaking instruction should be given more attention in EFL classes. More time and effort need to be exerted to develop the speaking skill and its sub skills. Some speaking activities and providing students with more opportunities to practice the oral language should be included.

- Incorporating some innovative strategies in the teachers ' guide that can be used by teachers.
- Designing curricula in a way that helps students to be more independent, more responsible for their learning giving them more authority in the learning process. Curriculum designers must consider the individual differences, the different cultures and backgrounds of the students

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